

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 – GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D3.4.1:

Use of materials produced from enzymatic processes to develop almost one sustainable alternative to current industrial processes.

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from M1 to M26
Periodic report date and version:	
Deliverable 3.4.1 Responsible	Elena Rosini
RM3 Responsible	Gianluigi Broggin

This report is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – M4C2 1.5 of PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU (Grant agreement no. ECS00000036)

Contents:

A. INTRODUCTION

A1. Production of new bio-polymers

A2. The valorization of textile waste blends

B. EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

B1. Modification of 4-vinyl guaiacol (4VG) structure to develop new biopolymers

B2. Development of an enzymatic treatment for degrading blended textile waste into value added products

Table - List of RM3 Project Deliverables

D. No	Name	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)	Status	Comments
D 3.1.1	Building of a database of identified chemicals in surface water	R	PU	M14		29/02/2024	Approved	
D 3.1.2	Case study applied to textile industry products	R	PU	M 14	21/03/2025		Pending	
D 3.4.1	Use of materials produced from enzymatic processes to develop almost one sustainable alternative to current industrial processes	Other (Material)	PU	M 26				
D 3.4.2	Identification of an innovative business model for the reconfiguration of textile production processes	Other (Material)	PU	M 26				
D 3.5.1	New products (Additives, auxiliary and finishing substances, dyes) for a textile supply chain	R/Other (Material)	PU	M 30				
D 3.5.2	Delineation of a ranking of chemicals or polymers (in case of microplastics) to be used with the local textile and chemical industries	Other (Material)	PU	M 32 (JULY 2025)				

A) INTRODUCTION

A1. Production of new bio-polymers

Notwithstanding the tremendous importance of synthetic polymers on the technological progress of modern society, the depletion of fossil sources used for plastic production, and pollution due to (micro)plastics accumulation in the environment raised great concern. Consequently, identification and application of new, renewable, and more sustainable raw-materials for (bio)polymer synthesis have enormous importance. For example, lignin-derived and terpenoid building-blocks derived from biomass are very promising and focused the efforts of many researchers [1,2]. In order to develop new sustainable bio-polymers capable to replace current commodity plastics, the application of sustainable catalytic polymerization processes is pivotal. Indeed, new functional monomers can be prepared from bio-based molecules allowing the application of controlled polymerization techniques such as ring-opening (co)polymerization [RO(CO)P] [3], and atom-transfer radical polymerization (ATRP) [4]. In this scenario, we selected 4-vinyl guaiacol (4-VG) as a bio-based platform molecule for the production of new bio-polymers with potential industrial applications. The 4-VG can be obtained from ferulic acid (FA), a naturally occurring phenolic acid, via biocatalytic processes [5]. In turn, FA can be recovered from several renewable resources such as bagasse, beetroot pulp, lignin and wheat bran, setting a concrete starting point for future application of envisaged new bio-plastics.

A2. The valorization of textile waste blends

The textile industry serves as a significant pillar of the global economy. Over the past two decades, global fiber production has nearly doubled and is projected to reach 149 million tons by 2030. However, only 15% of textiles are recycled, with the majority ending up in landfills where they decompose or are incinerated, posing a serious environmental threat [6]. Current data indicates that fiber production is predominantly based on polyester and cotton, which account for 54% and 22% of the annual output, respectively [7]. Enhancing the quality of materials often involves combining multiple fibers in a single textile, making recycling efforts more complex. In this scenario, enzymatic hydrolysis emerges as a promising solution for selectively processing material blends. This approach enables the efficient conversion of all components of blended polyester (polyethylene terephthalate, PET) textiles into high-value products using eco-friendly technologies. The performance of

commercial cellulases and an engineered Leaf-branch Compost Cutinase (LCC) [8] on pre- and post-consumer textile waste of various compositions (100% PET or polycotton, both dyed and undyed) has been evaluated. The aim was to selectively produce terephthalic acid (TPA), ethylene glycol (EG), and glucose. While PET-degrading enzymes effectively break PET down into its monomers (TPA and EG), processing substrates with high crystallinity remains a challenge. Consequently, physical pretreatments, such as thermal and ball-milling methods, have been evaluated to enhance PET depolymerization efficiency. The glucose released during the enzymatic hydrolysis of cotton will be used as a carbon source for the growth of an engineered *E. coli* strain [9] able of converting TPA into protocatechuic acid (PCA), a high-value product that can serve as a precursor in the production of pharmaceuticals and polymers.

B) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

BI. Modification of 4-vinyl guaiacol (4VG) structure to develop new biopolymers

The 4-VG is a multifunctional molecule, and its chemical structure presents a phenolic group and an olefin group offering the opportunity for chemical modification aimed at producing bio-based monomers and bio-polymers thereof. However, despite 4-VG potential applications in polymer chemistry, its functionalization and controlled polymerization is relatively underexplored.[10]

Depending on the functional group involved in the polymerization process, we envisaged the possibility to obtain two classes of 4-VG-based bio-polymers, namely polyolefins and polyesters, by using two different polymerization techniques, Activators ReGenerated by Electron Transfer (ARGET)-ATRP and organocatalytic ROCOP respectively. In both cases, the protection of 4-VG phenolic group is needed to obtain successful polymerization experiments. Thus, the acylation of commercial 4-VG to 4-vinyl guaiacol acetate (4-VGA) was investigated using acetic anhydride as the acylating agent. The synthesis of 4-VGA was successfully achieved, yielding the product with high purity and yield, i.e., > 99%, and > 90% respectively.

For the synthesis of bio-based thermoplastic polyolefins, the (ARGET)-ATRP of 4-VGA has been investigated by screening a variety of reaction conditions (e.g., temperature, initiator, catalyst, reductant), and the corresponding poly(vinyl-guaiacol acetate) (PVGA) has been obtained in good to high yields. In particular, polymerization kinetic

studies conducted under various reaction conditions revealed that 4-VGA reacts faster than styrene, the industrially most important aromatic vinyl monomer, producing polymer samples with higher molecular weights but larger distribution. For the synthesis of bio-based polyester polyols via organocatalytic ROCOP, the development of a multi-step procedure for the synthesis of new 4-epoxy guaiacol esters was necessary. At first, 4-VGA was further converted in the corresponding 4-epoxy guaiacol acetate (4-EGA) by classical epoxidation procedure, obtaining the desired monomer in good yield. The reaction of the new 4-EGA with phthalic anhydride has been used as benchmark for the optimization of copolymerization condition by varying a series of parameters (e.g., temperature, solvent, and organocatalyst). New poly(4-epoxyguaiacol acetate-alt-phthalic anhydride) (PEGA) polyester polyols have been successfully obtained in short times with high yields. Following these positive results, the multi-step monomer synthesis has been extended for the preparation of new epoxy-guaiacol esters with different acyl moieties. A series of new, structurally different, low molecular weight polyester polyols have been obtained via ROCOP of epoxy-guaiacol esters with several cyclic anhydrides.

Overall, the obtained results demonstrate a concrete starting point for the production of new 4-VG-based bio-polymers with numerous applications in polymer industry, such as in thermoplastic or polyurethanes formulations.

B2. Development of an enzymatic treatment for degrading blended textile waste into value added products

The hydrolytic activity of the S101N/F243T- Δ LCC enzyme variant was assessed using different pre- and post-consumer PET textile wastes, including white technical fabric, red-dyed apparel, mixed dyed non-woven fabric, high-tenacity safety belts, and pink polycotton fabric (70% PET, 30% cotton). Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis revealed high crystallinity value (35-47%) for all textile samples. A significant decrease in crystallinity was achieved by thermal treatment (up to 11-23%), while ball milling pre-treatment showed minimal impact.

- **Effect of pre-treatment methods on enzymatic activity** - The enzymatic activity of the S101N/F243T- Δ LCC enzyme was at first evaluated on 100% white PET fabric subjected to four physical-mechanical pre-treatments: ultrasound, microwave, ball milling, and thermal treatment. These methods are known to enhance enzymatic

accessibility by increasing surface area or reducing material crystallinity. Pre-treated textile samples (6-7 mg) were incubated with 50 μg (5.4 U) of the S101N/F243T- ΔLCC enzyme in 1.5 mL of 100 mM potassium phosphate buffer, pH 8.0, at 55 °C for four days under continuous rotation. Samples were collected at 0, 23, 47, 71, and 95 hours to quantify depolymerization products by HPLC analysis.

The results demonstrated TPA yields of approximately 94% for thermally treated samples, 10% for ball-milled samples, and 0% for untreated, ultrasound, or microwave-treated samples.

- **Enzymatic treatment of 100% PET textile samples** - Thermally and ball-milled pre-treated 100%PET textiles (10 mg) were incubated with 50 μg of the S101N/F243T- ΔLCC enzyme in 100 mM potassium phosphate buffer, pH 8.0, at 55 °C for 10 days. Thermally treated textiles achieved higher depolymerization yields (57-95%) compared to ball-milled samples (7-15%). After 10 days, white and red fabrics, along with safety belts, reached $\geq 95\%$ TPA yield. The thermally pre-treated white 100%PET fabric was processed on a larger scale, with 45 mg incubated with 500 μg of LCC enzyme. After 7 days, TPA was isolated resulting in a white powder, with an 84% yield,

- **Enzymatic treatment of polycotton textile samples** - Polycotton samples (45 mg) were pretreated via ball milling and hydrolyzed with the NS59150 cellulase cocktail (13.7 FPU per gram of textile) in 50 mM citrate buffer, pH 5.0, at 55 °C. Within 3 hours, enzymatic hydrolysis yielded $>95\%$ glucose. After cellulase treatment, the PET fibers remaining in the polycotton sample, were treated with the S101N/F243T- ΔLCC enzyme: after 11 days, a TPA yield of 60% was reached.

- **TPA conversion into value-added products** - Following polycotton hydrolysis, glucose-rich supernatants were added to *E. coli* K-12 MG1655 RARE cultures (Strain A, [9]) in autoinducing LB medium. Strain A, engineered to express terephthalate dioxygenase (TPADO α/β), reductase (TPADO RED), and zinc-dependent dehydrogenase (DCDDH), efficiently converted the previously recovered TPA into PCA with $>90\%$ yield in 24 hours, even at high TPA concentrations (up to 30 mM).

The proposed workflow integrates ball milling and cellulase hydrolysis for polycotton, followed by PET recovery and enzymatic depolymerization with the LCC variant. Purified TPA has been converted into PCA via the *E. coli* system, providing a scalable, high-yield bioconversion pathway for value-added products synthesis.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Graglia M. et al. (2015) *ChemBioEng Rev.* 2: 377-392
- [2] Della Monica F. and Kleij A.W. (2020) *Polym. Chem.* 11: 5109-5127
- [3] Santoro O. et al. (2022) *Sustain. Chem.* 3: 259-285
- [4] Rigo E. et al. (2023) *RSC Sustainability* 1: 788-813
- [5] Coghe S. et al. (2004) *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 52. 602–60810
- [6] Cucchiella F. and Gastaldi M. (2014) *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 33: 719
- [7] Textile Exchange, “Preferred Fiber & Materials Market Report”, 2022. Link: [Textile-Exchange_PFMR_2022.pdf](#) (textileexchange.org)
- [8] Pirillo V. et al. (2023) *FEBS J.* 290: 3185–3202
- [9] Rosini E. et al. (2025) Alanine enantiomers production from PET degradation: converting pollutants into valuable compounds. Submitted
- [10] Rigo E. et al. (2024) *Molecules* 29: 2507